
ASCAT Twice-Daily SIR-Enhanced Scatterometer *EASE-Grid 2.0* Radar Backscatter

Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document

Version 1.1

December 31, 2024

David G. Long¹, Julie Z. Miller²

¹ *Microwave Earth Remote Sensing Laboratory, Brigham Young University, Provo, UT, USA*

² *Earth Science and Observation Center, Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, USA*

Cover Image

Color montage of morning overpass AMSR2 horizontally-polarized 36 GHz passive microwave brightness temperatures, 29–30 June, 2003, by M. J. Brodzik, National Snow and Ice Data Center.

Citation

David G. Long and Julie Z. Miller. 2024. ASCAT Twice-Daily SIR-Enhanced Scatterometer EASE-Grid 2.0 Radar Backscatter Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document, Version 1.0. NSIDC White Paper. <https://doi.org/TBD>.

Contents

1	Revision History	5
2	Acronyms and Abbreviations	6
3	Purpose of this Document	8
4	Gridded and SIR-Enhanced Product Description	10
4.1	Product Description	10
4.2	ASCAT Instrument	10
4.2.1	ASCAT Temporal-Spatial Sampling	11
4.3	Grid Spatial Extent	16
4.4	Grid Spatial Resolution	16
4.5	Data Products	17
5	Algorithm Description	20
5.1	Background	20
5.2	ASCAT Backscatter Image Products	20
5.3	Radar Spatial Response and Image Reconstruction	21
5.3.1	Local-Time-of-Day	24
5.4	Sample Data	26
6	Measurement Modeling	30
6.1	Incidence Angle Effects	30
6.2	Azimuth Angle Effects	32
6.3	Data Volume	37
7	Acknowledgements	39
8	References	40
	Appendices	44
A	ASCAT Projections and Grids	44
B	ASCAT Data Definition	45
B.1	File Requirements	45
B.2	Filename Convention	45
B.3	File Content, v1.0	46

List of Figures

1	ASCAT observation swath	9
2	ASCAT measurement theory illustrations	11
3	SRF response footprint examples	12
4	swath coverage near the North pole illustrating a polar pass	13
5	One day of ASCAT North Pole coverage	15
6	Northern and Southern EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents	16
7	Cylindrical EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents	17
8	EASE2-M vs. EASE2-T extents	18
9	25 km nested resolutions	18
10	GRD vs. SIR component measurement concept	21
11	ASCAT LTOD histograms	25
12	Northern Hemisphere A images examples	26
13	Southern Hemisphere A images examples	27
14	Global A images examples	28
15	Zoom-in Northern Hemisphere A images examples	29
16	Antarctica VV σ^o and σ^o slope images	30
17	VV azimuth angle relative to north versus incidence angle for Antarctic study region	31
18	Incidence versus azimuth angles for the Antarctic study region	34
19	σ^o versus azimuth angle in an Antarctic study area	35
20	Azimuth modulation model coefficients in Antarctic study area	36
21	Antarctica VV σ^o and σ^o slope images	37
22	Southern Hemisphere VV σ^o azimuth model coefficient images	38

List of Tables

1	ATBD Revision History	5
2	Data Set Revision History	5
3	List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	6
4	ASCAT Grids	17
5	Available twice-daily ASCAT image products. ASCAT operates at only VV polarization.	19
6	25 km Projections and Grid Dimensions	44
7	Filenaming Convention	46

1 Revision History

Table 1: ATBD Revision History

Revision	Date	Purpose
1.0	2023-01-05	Initial Version
1.1	2023-06-03	Update information azimuth products

Table 2: Data Set Revision History

Revision	Date	Purpose
1.0	2023-01-05	Initial Data Release

2 Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 3: List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

ADEOS	Advanced Earth Observing Satellite
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
AVE	weighted AVeraging image formation algorithm
BYU	Brigham Young University
CDR	Climate Data Record
CETB	Calibrated Passive Microwave Daily EASE-Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature
CF	Climate and Forecast Metadata Conventions
DAAC	Distributed Active Archive Center
dB	decibel ($10 \log_{10}$)
DDP	Digital Doppler Processor
DIB	Drop-In-the-Bucket averaging (used to produce GRD products)
DOY	Day Of Year
E2N	EASE-Grid 2.0, Northern Hemisphere Projection
E2S	EASE-Grid 2.0, Southern Hemisphere Projection
E2T	EASE-Grid 2.0, Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical Projection
EASE-Grid	Equal-Area Scalable Earth Grid (Original Definition)
EASE-Grid 2.0	Equal-Area Scalable Earth Grid Version 2.0
EASE2-M	EASE-Grid 2.0, Mid- and Low-Latitude Cylindrical Projection
EASE2-N	EASE-Grid 2.0, Northern Hemisphere Projection
EASE2-S	EASE-Grid 2.0, Southern Hemisphere Projection
EASE2-T	EASE-Grid 2.0, Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical Projection
EIA	Earth Incidence Angle
EOSDIS	Earth Observing System Data and Information System
ESA	European Space Agency
ESDR	Earth System Data Record
EUMETSAT	European Meteorological Satellite organization
FA	incidence-angle Fixed Azimuth modulation coefficients
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FCDR	Fundamental Climate Data Record
GHz	GigaHertz
GRD	(Drop-In-the-Bucket) Gridding Method
LFM	linear frequency modulation
LTOD	local-time-of-day
MEaSURES	Making Earth System Data Records for Use in Research Environments
Metop	mission name

Acronyms and Abbreviations

MHz	MegaHertz
MRF	Measurement Response Function
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NSCAT	NASA Scatterometer
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NSIDC	National Snow and Ice Data Center
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
PRF	Pulse Repetition Frequency
PSRF	Pixel Spatial Response Function
rSIR	radiometer version of SIR
SCP	Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder
SDR	Sensor Data Record
Sigma-0	normalized radar cross section or backscatter (σ^0)
SIR	Scatterometer Image Reconstruction
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
VA	incidence-angle Variable Azimuth modulation coefficients
VV	Vertical-polarization transmit, Vertical-polarization receive

3 Purpose of this Document

This document describes a CETB-compatible radar backscatter product created from Advanced Scatterometer (ASCAT) 5.225 GHz radar observations collected during the ASCAT-on-Metop mission in 2006–present.

ASCAT Stoffelen et al. (2017) collected nominally ~ 6 km resolution normalized radar cross section (σ^o) from 6 different azimuth angles over two 550 km wide swaths with a 672 km gap. ASCAT employed long, fan-beam antennas with narrow beamwidths, see Fig. 1. Along-beam resolution was achieved using 5 ms linear frequency modulated transmit pulses and FFT-based processing. Nominally 25 km σ^o measurements were reported by combining FFT bins. The individual beams were reported in the highest resolution data, termed ‘SZF’. The SZF bins extended beyond the nominal swath width to lower and higher incidence angles. The calibration this extended swath is not considered as accurate as those over the nominal wind swath. The σ^o measurements collected by each beam in sequence span from low ($\sim 15^\circ$) incidence angles near the nadir track to larger (up to 63°) at the outer edge of the extended swath. The multiple beams provided azimuth diversity of the σ^o measurements, which is required to retrieve the surface wind (Stoffelen et al., 2017) (Ulaby and Long, 2014) (Naderi et al., 1991)

While designed and optimized for ocean observation, ASCAT also collected σ^o measurements over land and ice. The observed σ^o depends on the surface roughness, geometry, and dielectric constant. These depend on geophysical parameters of interest such as surface freeze/thaw state, snow and ice structure, moisture content, and vegetation characteristics, among others (Ulaby and Long, 2014). The ASCAT data set provides a unique “snapshot” of the Earth during its mission lifetime.

The ASCAT radar backscatter (ASCAT) product exploits the ASCAT measurements to create a unique backscatter image data set that captures the state of the Earth during the ASCAT mission (1996-1997). To exploit this data, we employ image reconstruction techniques to create daily and twice-daily conventional resolution and enhanced resolution ASCAT radar images from the measurements. The new data set is provided to the science community to support cryosphere and climate studies.

Figure 1: ASCAT observation swath. Nominally 25 km σ^0 measurements are collected over two 550 km wind swaths separated by a nadir gap. Measurements are not collected over the central (nadir) gap (Stoffelen et al., 2017). The antenna footprint width on the ground varies from approximately 19 km to 35 km.

4 Gridded and SIR-Enhanced Product Description

4.1 Product Description

The *ASCAT* product includes Level 1 gridded, twice-daily, radar backscatter data collected at 5.225 GHz with vertical transmit-vertical receive [VV] polarization. Data are gridded to the EASE-Grid 2.0 Azimuthal and Cylindrical projections (Brodzik et al., 2012)(Brodzik et al., 2014), at two spatial resolutions, as described below. The *ASCAT* product is archived and distributed by the National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center (<https://nsidc.org/data/NSIDC-TBD/versions/1>).

Input data for the *ASCAT* v1.0 product are the *ASCAT* SZF Sigma0 files obtained through NOAA from ESA (EUMETSAT, 2014). Using the quality flags in the input data, only the highest quality measurements are included in *ASCAT* product. The data coverage is global for the period beginning in Oct. 2006 through the present. No calibration corrections were applied to the data.

4.2 ASCAT Instrument

ASCAT flew as a primary payload on three different Metop satellites. *ASCAT-A*, which flew on Metop-B, was launched on Oct. 2006 from Guiana and operated for nearly 15 years before being shutoff in Nov. 2021. *ASCAT-B*, which flew on Metop-A, was launched in 2012 and continues operation as of 2024. *ASCAT-C*, which flew on Metop-C, was launched in Nov. 2018 and continues operation as of 2024. The Metop satellites flew in a sun-synchronous 800 km circular polar orbits with an orbit inclination angle of 98.7°. The spacecraft are nominally separated by about one half orbit.

The *ASCAT* instrument is described in Stoffelen et al. (2017), Gelsthorpe et al. (2000), EUMETSAT (2022). *ASCAT* is a fan-beam Doppler range-gate scatterometer that uses pulse-compression to achieve along-beam resolution (Ulaby and Long, 2014) like its predecessor the ERS-1 scatterometer (Attema, 1991)(Lin et al., 2017), though with 6 beams in a dual swath instead of 3 beams and a single-side swath. The *ASCAT* instrument employs six 3 m long fan-beam antennas deployed to provide three VV polarized azimuth angle observations on each side of the spacecraft, see Fig. 1. Along-track resolution is provided by the narrow beamwidth of the antenna beams and the pulse timing. Along-beam resolution is provided via pulse compression of a 10 ms linear frequency modulated (LFM) pulse, illustrated in Fig. 2.

Multiple pulses are processed and summed into a single measurement. The SRF of an individual SZF σ^0 measurements is defined by the range-gate timing bin limits and the antenna gain pattern¹. Examples of the SRF for several *ASCAT* measurements are illustrated

¹Note that while a radiometer's footprint is defined by the antenna pattern, the radar footprint is defined by the antenna pattern squared due to the two-way travel of the signal from radar to the surface and back,

Figure 2: ASCAT measurement theory illustrations. Intersection of the fan-beam footprint and isorange lines used to define the along-beam resolution. (Ulaby and Long, 2014)

in Fig. 3. The SRF, which varies for each measurement and beams, defines the intrinsic resolution of the measurement (Long and Stroeve, 2011). The SRFs of measurements along the beam overlap at the 3 dB level.

ASCAT collected return echo power measurements, which were converted into σ^o using the radar equation (EUMETSAT, 2022)(Ulaby and Long, 2014). The σ^o value depends on the surface roughness, geometry, and dielectric constant (Ulaby and Long, 2014). Multiple SZF measurements from each beam are combined into lower resolution (25 km) measurements prior to wind retrieval. However, high resolution ('slice' SZF) measurements are also reported and are the only ones used in this product.

As described below, from these σ^o measurements twice-daily global images were created by (1) DIB gridding of the σ^o measurements on a 25 km grid and (2) applying the SIR algorithm to enhance the effective resolution of the data by exploiting the irregular patterns of measurement locations and signal oversampling (from overlaps in adjacent footprints and overlapping swaths). The SIR images are reported on a 3.125 km grid.

4.2.1 ASCAT Temporal-Spatial Sampling

As previously noted, ASCAT uses 6 fan beam antennas to cover two swaths separated by a nadir gap, see Fig. fig:swathlayout. On each side one beam points forward, one points to the side, and one points backward. As the spacecraft flies overhead, a given point in the swath is first observed by a forward-facing beam, then by the mid-beam, and finally by the aft-facing beam. The worst-case time span between fore and aft measurements is less than about 3 min.

by range-gate timing, and by signal processing of the signal (Ulaby and Long, 2014).

Figure 3: Illustrative examples of the spatial gain pattern response of mid-swath ASCAT σ^0 measurements from (top) a forward-looking beam and (bottom) the mid-beam. The lines are contours drawn at 3, 6, and 10 dB below the peak gain. (Lindsley et al., 2016)

Figure 4: ASCAT swath coverage near the North pole illustrating a polar pass. The pole is in the center. The dashed circle corresponds to 60°N . The lines radiating out from the center depict hourly boundaries. (left) Light blue indicates measurements flagged as Ascending in the SZF file, while yellow denotes measurements flagged as Descending. The green area contains both ascending- and descending-flagged measurements. (right) Idealized ascending/descending flagging of individual measurements, which in this case corresponds to LTOD division into morning and evening intervals.

An orbit can be divided into ascending and descending portions depend on the north-south velocity of the spacecraft.

When the satellite reaches its most northern point the pass transitions from ascending to descending. Before this occurs the satellite measures forward from that transition point, and after the transition the satellite continues to measure aft of that transition point. This causes a double trapazoidal region where the forward-looking measurements are still ascending, but the aft-looking measurements descending. Figure 4 is a diagram illustrates how the measurements of a single pass of the outer beam are divided into ascending and descending passes. Note that the ascending/descending flag reported in the data is based on the satellite nadir position and does not take into account the rotation of the antenna. Thus, there is an overlap region of measurements flagged ascending with those flagged ascending. This region of pass overlap is a primary cause for temporal resolution loss in ascending/descending images due to the overlap area that measurements separated by only a few minutes. The resulting images share temporally overlapping data thus suffer from diminished temporal resolution. In contrast, when the data is divided by LTOD or proper

ascending/descending, the division is appropriately sharp.

Figure 4 also illustrates the local time transition that occurs in the Arctic region. Note the wide span of local time hours along the swath. Because the green region of overlap for each pass is closely located to the poles, it covers many lines of longitude and thus has a large variation in LTOD. In the polar regions, splitting the data by LTOD rather than ascending/descending is advantageous.

Figure 5 illustrates polar coverage over a day as function of time. Because the satellite orbits the earth every 100 minutes, there are approximately 14.25 orbits/day in a pattern that approximately repeats every 4 days².

²The actual exact repeat cycle was typically much longer and varied through the mission. Nonetheless, it remains approximately 4 days.

Figure 5: Illustration of ASCAT swath coverage near the North pole over one UTC day. The pole is in the center. Left column shows morning LTOD-flagged measurements, while the right column evening LTOD-flagged measurements. Yellow shows measurements within the current 24-hr period, while green indicates measurements associated with the previous day and light brown shows measurements associated with the following day, see text. (top row) One continuous orbit [recall that the ASCAT swath is split into left and right sides]. (second row) Two orbits. (third) Eight orbits. (bottom) All orbits in one UTC day.

Figure 6: Northern and Southern EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents. The land-ocean mask from Brodzik and Knowles (2011).

4.3 Grid Spatial Extent

Azimuthal *ASCAT* grids extend to the full Northern (EASE2-N) and Southern (EASE2-S) hemispheres (Fig. 6), as described in Brodzik et al. (2012, 2014). The spatial extent of the equal-area cylindrical projections (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8) is defined to match the extent of compatible grids favored by two user communities: (1) the Mid-Latitude (EASE2-M) grid, extending to $\pm 85.0445664^\circ$ latitude, has been adopted by the SMAP user community. And, (2) the Temperate and Tropical (EASE2-T) grid, limited to latitudes equatorward of $\pm 67.1^\circ$, is consistent with the original CETB products defined for similar scanning radiometers (Brodzik et al., 2021). See Appendix A Table 6 for grid specifications.

4.4 Grid Spatial Resolution

ASCAT grid resolutions are defined relative to a 25 km base resolution, i.e., 25 km and 3.125 km MEaSURES CETB data products (Brodzik et al., 2021). Nested resolutions relative to the CETB 25 km base grids are defined using exact divisors of 2, as illustrated in Figure 9. *ASCAT* projection extents, dimensions and grid cell size details are included in Appendix A. Grids used for *ASCAT* processing are included in Table 4.

Figure 7: Cylindrical EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents. Full extent coverage is EASE2-M, with horizontal red lines delineating the smaller latitudinal extent of the EASE2-T grid. The land-ocean mask is from Brodzik and Knowles (2011).

Table 4: ASCAT EASE-Grid 2.0 base grids produced by the projection and reconstruction algorithm. See Section 5 for GRD and SIR reconstruction details.

EASE2-M	EASE2-N	EASE2-S	EASE2-T
n/a	25km (GRD)	25km (GRD)	25km (GRD)
n/a	3.125km (AVE/SIR)	3.125km (AVE/SIR)	3.125km (AVE/SIR)

4.5 Data Products

The ASCAT product at the NSIDC DAAC covers the period beginning 14 Sept 1996 (DOY 258) through 28 June 1997 (DOY 179). No calibration corrections were applied to the data. In creating a time series, a “moving average” approach was used with overlapping imaging periods that start on a mission day and extend through the desired 1-, 2-, or 4-day period (or to the end of the mission, whichever comes first). 1-day and 2-day images start every mission day. 4-day images start every other mission day. Table 5 summarizes the available ASCAT products, which are all in CETB-standard EASE-2 Grid projections.

Figure 8: Relationship of EASE-Grid 2.0 cylindrical projection extents. The EASE2-T extent is defined for compatibility with the CETB products. (Difference in latitudinal extent is exaggerated, see Fig. 7 for actual difference in projected extent (Brodzik et al., 2021)).

Figure 9: CETB nested grids based on a 25 km base resolution. Only 25 km and 3.125 km divisions are used in ASCAT products (Long et al., 2019).

Table 5: Available twice-daily ASCAT image products. ASCAT operates at only VV polarization.

Image Period	Algorithm	Pix. Res. (km)	Regions*	Size [†] N/S/T (MB)
1,2,4	GRD	25	N,S,T	6/6/9
1,2,4	AVE	3.125	N,S,T	531/531/768
1,2,4	SIR	3.125	N,S,T	531/531/768

* Region code: N=Northern Hemisphere, S=Southern Hemisphere, T=Global

† Uncompressed size. Compressed sizes vary but are 30-40% of compressed sizes.

5 Algorithm Description

5.1 Background

The *effective resolution* of an image is defined by the *pixel spatial response function* (PSRF), where the effective resolution is given by the dimension(s) of the one-half power (3-dB) extent of the PSRF. In contrast, the *measurement response function* (MRF) describes the spatial characteristics of the *individual* measurements that were combined to create the image. For a radar, the MRF depends on the two-way antenna gain pattern, the scan geometry, and the signal processing. For both radars and radiometers, the PSRF depends on the MRF and the image formation algorithm. In a linear image formation algorithm, the reported pixel value consists of the weighted sum of nearby measurements. In this case the PSRF is then the normalized weighted sum of the measurement MRF functions, including their spatial offset from the center of the pixel.

The spacing of pixels is termed the “pixel posting” or the “posting resolution”. In creating the *ASCAT* backscatter image product, multiple measurements from different passes are combined into single pixel values. The resulting image pixels have an effective resolution slightly coarser than the posting resolution since (1) the measurements are not all centered the same, and (2) their MRFs can extend outside of the pixel area. The PSRF provides the tool for defining the effective pixel resolution (Long and Brodzik, 2016a). In order to be compatible with the CETB data set, two posting resolutions are considered: 25 km and 3.125 km, see Fig. 10. The former is used only for gridded (DIB) products while the latter is used for enhanced resolution products such as AVE and SIR.

5.2 ASCAT Backscatter Image Products

The *ASCAT* backscatter products include both low-noise (low-resolution) coarse resolution GRD images and higher-noise (enhanced) fine-resolution (SIR) images. The various products have their advantages and disadvantages. Multiple image types allow users the flexibility of choosing the appropriate images for their research application.

To create radar CETB-compatible products, different approaches are used for each resolution. Because the sensor was not designed as an imager, there are gaps between the measurements that must be filled by combining multiple passes over an extended imaging period. As a result of the 4 day near-repeat cycle, multiple imaging periods are defined³: 1 day, 2 day and 4 day. These provide a user-selectable tradeoff between temporal resolution, spatial resolution, and noise.

For GRD images, the source backscatter measurements are gridded onto a 25 km grid using DIB techniques. In this approach, all the measurements whose center location falls

³Ideally, an 8 day period would be included to improve azimuth sampling with an LTOD, but this was not done due to computational limitations.

Figure 10: Conceptual illustration of coarse 25 km (left) vs. high resolution 3.125 km (right) pixels. The ellipses represent the individual MRFs of the measurements (the actual shapes are more complicated than this.) DIB is used for GRD images while AVE and SIR are used for high resolution images.

within a grid element are averaged into the reported value. For the 3.125 km product, the source measurements are processed using the the first iteration of the SIR algorithm, termed ‘AVE’. AVE images are weighted averages of the measurements which cover the pixel, where the weighting is based on the measurement MRF, which varies from measurement to measurement. Along with each measurement’s MRF, the SIR algorithm exploits the irregular patterns of the measurement locations and signal oversampling from overlaps in adjacent footprints and overlapping passes. Table 5 summarizes the image product types.

5.3 Radar Spatial Response and Image Reconstruction

The effective spatial resolution of an image product is determined by the MRF of the sensor and by the image formation algorithm used. As previously noted, the MRF is determined by the antenna gain pattern, the scan geometry (notably the antenna scan angle), and the signal processing, see Long et al. (1993), Long (2017), Lindsley et al. (2016). The goal in forming a σ^o image is to estimate the backscatter properties of the surface from noisy measurements that employ (possibly variable) MRFs that sample the surface. Though simple to implement, DIB techniques ignore the MRF, which limits their effective resolution. Reconstruction techniques that use the MRF can provide much finer effective resolution.

Reconstruction processing techniques effectively assume the underlying signal (the backscatter) being sampled is band-limited, which is the only consistent assumption possible with sampled data (Long and Brodzik, 2016b, Long and Franz, 2016b). For reconstruction, the backscatter at each point of a fine-scale pixel grid is estimated, producing a backscatter

image or map. While the image is generated on a regular grid, the measurement locations and MRF are not aligned with the grid, and so the measurements form an irregular sampling pattern, which can complicate signal reconstruction. Many commonly used image formation algorithms either ignore this (as is done in DIB) or attempt to interpolate or distance-weight the measurements values. In using image reconstruction, we avoid these ad hoc, non-optimal approaches and explicitly compute the MRF of each measurement as part of the reconstruction process. This is computationally intense, but provides the best possible image construction. The remainder of this section outlines this process.

An individual scatterometer backscatter measurement z_i can be modeled as the integral of the product of the MRF and the surface backscatter, i.e.,

$$z_i = \iint \text{MRF}_i(x, y; pp) \sigma^o(x, y, \theta, \phi_i, t, pp) dx dy + \text{noise} \quad (1)$$

where $\text{MRF}_i(x, y; pp)$ is the spatial MRF of the i^{th} measurement at x, y and the surface σ^o depends on spatial location x, y , incidence angle θ , azimuth angle ϕ , time t , and polarization pp , i.e.,

$$\text{MRF}_i(x, y; pp) = \iint \frac{G_a^2(x, y; pp) G_p(x, y; pp)}{R^4(x, y)}. \quad (2)$$

where

$$X = \iint \frac{G_a^2(x, y; pp) G_p(x, y; pp)}{R^4(x, y)} dx dy. \quad (3)$$

where $G_a(x, y; pp)$ is the effective two-way antenna gain at the surface at (x, y) for polarization pp , $G_p(x, y; pp)$ is the processor gain, and $R(x, y)$ is the slant range from the radar to the surface. Note that the measurement is an average of σ^o in spatial coordinates as well as in azimuth and incidence angles.

Eq. 1 is discretized on the imaging grid to become

$$z_i = \sum_{j \in \text{image}} h_{ij} a_j + \text{noise} \quad (4)$$

where a_j is the backscatter at the center of the j^{th} pixel at (x_l, y_k) and $h_{ij} = \text{MRF}(x_l, y_k; \phi_i)$ is the discretely sampled MRF for the i -th measurement evaluated at the j -th pixel center where h_{ij} is normalized so that $\sum_j h_{ij} = 1$. In practice, the MRF is negligible some distance from the measurement center, so the sums need only be computed over a small area around the pixel. Ignoring the noise, Eq. 4 can be written as the matrix equation

$$\vec{Z} = \mathbf{H} \vec{a} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{H} contains the sampled MRF for each measurement and \vec{Z} and \vec{a} are vectors composed of the measurements z_i and a_j , respectively. Even for small images, \mathbf{H} is large and

sparse, and may be over-determined or under-determined depending on the number and locations of the measurements. Reconstruction of the surface σ^o is equivalent to inverting Eq. 5.

The iterative SIR algorithm (Early and Long, 2001)(Long et al., 1993) is a particular reconstruction algorithm that is specifically developed for scatterometer image formation. SIR approximates a maximum-entropy solution to an under-determined equation and a least-squares solution to an over-determined system. The first iteration of SIR is termed 'AVE' (for weighted AVErage) and provides a simple reconstruction estimate that is refined in later SIR iterations. The AVE estimate of the j -th pixel is given by

$$a_j = \frac{\sum_i h_{ij} z_i}{\sum_i h_{ij}} \quad (6)$$

where the sums are over all measurements that have non-negligible MRF at the pixel. The SIR iteration begins with an initial image a_j^0 whose pixels are set to the AVE values defined in Eq. 6. Thereafter, the iterative equation for single-variate SIR is given by

$$a_j^{k+1} = \frac{\sum_i u_{ij}^k h_{ij}}{\sum_i h_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

where

$$u_{ij}^k = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{1}{2p_i^k} \left(1 - \frac{1}{d_i^k} \right) + \frac{1}{a_j^k d_i^k} \right]^{-1} & d_i^k \geq 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} p_i^k (1 - d_i^k) + a_j^k d_i^k & d_i^k < 1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$d_i^k = \left(\frac{z_i}{p_i^k} \right)^\lambda \quad (9)$$

where $d_i^k = (s_i/p_i^k)^\lambda$ with $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$. The factor d_i^k is the square root of the ratio of a measurement to its forward projection at the k^{th} iteration. The update term u_{ij}^k is a non-linear function of both d_i^k and the previous image a_j^k . The sigmoid-like non-linearity in Eq. 8 constrains the amount of change permitted during any one iteration, thereby minimizing the effects of noise Long et al. (1993). Though not used in this paper, a spatial median filter can be applied to the image between iterations to further reduce the noise Long et al. (1993).

For scatterometers, SIR is implemented in dB (Long, 2017)(Early and Long, 2001)(Long et al., 1993); i.e., the computation is done on $10 \log_{10}(z_i)$ rather than on the linear-space value z_i as done in the radiometer version of SIR (Long and Brodzik, 2016a)(Long and Daum, 1998). In considering the differences between linear and dB processing, recall the well-known fact that computing the arithmetic mean of values in dB is equivalent to computing $10 \log_{10}$ of the geometric mean of the linear-space values (Wikipedia, 2016). With the measurements in dB, the reconstruction processing can be viewed as a form of weighted

geometric mean filtering. Since it has been found that geometric mean filters are better at reducing Gaussian-type noise and preserving linear features than (linear) arithmetic mean filters (Pitas and Venetsanopoulos, 1986), some performance advantage to dB processing is expected and observed (Long, 2017). The linear and dB computations yield similar, but slightly different results, due to the varying signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the measurements and limited signal dynamic range (Long, 2017).

In practice, since the σ^o measurements are quite noisy, attempting full image reconstruction can produce excessive noise enhancement. In general, more iterations improve the signal and resolution, but also increase the noise level. To reduce noise enhancement and resulting artifacts, regularization can be employed, at the expense of resolution (Long and Franz, 2016a)(Early and Long, 2001)(Long et al., 1993)(Long, 2017). Regularization is a smoothing constraint introduced in an inverse problem to prevent extreme values or over-fitting. Regularization results in partial or incomplete reconstruction of the signal (Long and Franz, 2016a). It also creates a trade off between signal reconstruction accuracy and noise enhancement. SIR includes regularization achieved by prematurely terminating the iteration. Based on simulations and confirmed by analysis of actual data, 20-30 iterations provides a nice trade off result. We note that for a noisy sensor like a scatterometer, the results are not particularly sensitive to the precise value chosen, hence a fixed value can be selected. Selection of the number of iterations is based on simulation, see citeearly2001, Long et al. (1993) and Long (2017). For this product, a fixed (30) number of SIR iterations is employed for both binary and full response MRFs.

5.3.1 Local-Time-of-Day

As previously noted, the goal of image reconstruction is to estimate the surface σ^o from the sensor σ^o measurements. Measurements from multiple orbit passes over a narrow local time window are combined. When multiple measurements are combined, the resulting images represent a temporal average of the measurements over the averaging period. There is an implicit assumption that the surface characteristics remain constant over the imaging period For both conventional-resolution (GRD) and enhanced-resolution (SIR) images.

The radar backscatter of a natural surface is a strong function of the state of the water it contains, i.e., frozen or thawed. As a result of the sun-synchronous orbit geometry, the radar observations at a given location on the earth fall within two narrow diurnal windows. At the equator, these correspond to the ascending and descending orbit passes. This can be exploited to provide twice-daily sampling. Thus, *ASCAT* images on the cylindrical *EASE-Grid 2.0* projections are separated by ascending and descending passes. A separate image ("both") product is also made that combines both which achieves between spatial coverage at the expense of temporal resolution.

Near the poles, the temporal windows widen to several hours but remain relatively narrow. Since surface temperatures can fluctuate widely during the day, daily averaging is

Figure 11: Histograms of typical measurement LTOD for ASCAT measurements falling within a 1° latitude band at (left) 30° – 31° N and (right) 60° – 61° N over one day. This plot was created using measurements from both ASCAT-A and ASCAT-B since both have similar (though not identical) distributions, as does ASCAT-C. All measurements fall into essentially one of two narrow LTOD time periods, centered at approximately 03:30 h and 15:30 h in the Northern Hemisphere. Although the center time varies with latitude, any point on Earth is observed at one of two times within ± 90 min.

not generally useful at these locations, since it smears diurnal temperature fluctuations in the averaged σ° . However, it is reasonable to split the data into two distinct images per day, using intervals based on local-time-of-day (LTOD), thereby only combining measurements with a similar LTOD. This minimizes the fluctuations in the observed backscatt at high latitudes due to changes in physical temperature from daily temperature cycling.

The ASCAT images on the azimuthal projections are separated into twice-daily, morning and evening passes based on observation LTOD, in addition to images that combine the two. At low latitudes, which typically have few overlapping swaths at similar LTOD in the same day, LTOD division is equivalent to ascending/descending division. An ancillary data array is included in each file, to describe the effective time average of the measurements combined into the pixel for a particular day. This enables investigators to explicitly account for the LTOD temporal variation of the measurements included in a particular pixel. A separate image ("both") product is also made that combines both which achieves greater spatial coverage at the expense of temporal resolution.

Histograms of the LTOD of the sensor's measurements falling within two narrow latitude bands are shown in Fig. 11. For the ASCAT orbit, a natural division in the measurement LTOD is at approximately 03:30 and 15:30 h. For consistency with Long and Brodzik (2016b) and Brodzik et al. (2021), the ASCAT data are produced using this LTOD division. Note how the LTOD falls within one of two tight groups that correspond to the ascending and descending orbit passes, and that there are natural divisions in the measurement

LTOD at 00:00 and 12:00 hrs. Thus, the measurements provide twice-daily sampling. Note that when more than day's worth of data is combined, the LTOD division is maintained so that a multi-day morning image combines only morning observations and evening images only contain evening observations. Images marked as "both" Combine all available data that passes quality checks for the imaging period. For global projections (T), ascending-only and descend-only images combine all data marked as ascending or descending, respectively.

5.4 Sample Data

Figures 12–14 present examples of 4-day product images for each polarization and region where all passes ('both') within the imaging period are combined. Swath-like artifacts over the oceans are the result of significant temporal variation of surface σ^o due to wind changes during the imaging interval. Over the ocean high winds correspond to higher average σ^o values while low winds correspond to low wind speeds. Since the measurements are averaged over multiple days, the ocean values are not considered particularly useful. Land and ice backscatter is much more stable.

Figure 15 compares the GRD, AVE, and SIR images of an area in northeast Greenland. Note the improve contrast and resolution of the SIR images relative to GRD, with AVE falling between the two. Additional data visualization are provided in later sections.

Figure 12: Visualizations of examples of 4-day (DOY 3-6, 2007) ASCAT-A (left) A (σ^o at 40° incidence angle) and (right) B (slope of σ^o versus incidence angle in dB/deg at 40° incidence angle) polarizations. Images have been reduced in resolution for presentation here.

Figure 13: Visualizations of examples of 4-day (DOY 3-6, 2007) ASCAT-A (left) A (σ^o at 40° incidence angle) and (right) B (slope of σ^o versus incidence angle in dB/deg at 40° incidence angle) polarizations. Images have been reduced in resolution for presentation here.

Figure 14: Visualizations of examples of 4-day (DOY 3-6, 2007) ASCAT-A (top) A (σ^o at 40° incidence angle) and (bottom) B (slope of σ^o versus incidence angle in dB/deg at 40° incidence angle) polarizations. Images have been reduced in resolution for presentation here.

Figure 15: Zoom-in views of 4-day (DOY 3-6, 2007) ASCAT-A A (σ° at 40° incidence angle) for (top left) SIR, (top right) AVE, and (bottom left) GRD.

6 Measurement Modeling

To dive deeper into the backscatter data and the performance of the imaging algorithms, a coastal region is employed to visualize the differences between the products at fine resolution.

Figure 16: Zoom-in of a Southern Hemisphere VV focusing on Antarctica (left) σ^o (A) and (right) σ^o slope (B) images for DOY 003-007, 2007.

6.1 Incidence Angle Effects

Over natural surfaces σ^o depends on the measurement incidence angle. Since ASCAT is a fan-beam system, it collects σ^o measurements over a range of incidence angles ranging from about 15° to 60° . The variation in incidence angle must be accounted for when combining multiple measurements. The incidence angle normalization $\gamma^o = \sigma^o / \cos \theta$ where θ is the incidence angle is sometimes used. However, the slope of this correction is strictly downward and since upward slopes are observed in some areas, this normalization is not used. Further, this normalization is based on specific backscatter model which does not apply to all natural surface. Instead, following prior investigators, see Long et al. (1993), Long and Miller (2023), and references therein, a linear slope is used that is centered at 40° , i.e., σ^o as a function of incidence angle is modelled according to

$$\sigma^o = A + B(\theta - 40^\circ) \quad (10)$$

where A is σ^o at 40° incidence angle; B is the slope of σ^o versus incidence angle θ . At each pixel, the model parameters A (the mean σ^o), B (the normalized slope of σ^o versus incidence angle) are estimated from the backscatter measurements on a pixel by pixel basis.

Figure 17: (top) VV polarization azimuth angle relative to north versus incidence angle from DOYs 3-6, 2007 from within the (bottom) outlined location of a particular Antarctic study region.

The model parameters (A and B) are estimated from observations only from measurements with incidence angle greater than 20° .

Figure 16 illustrates A and B images of Antarctica that were extracted from Southern Hemisphere AVE (all pass) products. A specific small study area is defined in Fig. 17 and a plot of the SZF σ° versus incidence angle for measurements falling in this study area is shown. Note the linear dependence of σ° in dB with incidence.

6.2 Azimuth Angle Effects

Periodic natural surfaces exhibit variations in σ° with azimuth angle, including water waves Ulaby and Long (2014), Naderi et al. (1991), sastrugi⁴ and snow dunes (Long and Drinkwater, 2000)(Lindsley and Long, 2016)(Ashcraft and Long, 2006), and sand dunes Stephen and Long (2007). The measured σ° is thus a function of the azimuth direction from which the surface is observed. Scatterometers such as ASCAT are *designed* to make multi-azimuth observations during a single pass over the ocean to exploit this effect for wind-driven wave in order to estimate the near-surface wind Naderi et al. (1991). However, these measurements intrinsically coarse since they must be made in a single pass. Unlike the ocean, land and ice features do not (generally) change as rapidly so observations from multiple passes can be combined.

Over the course of the orbit's repeat cycle each point on the surface can be observed at multiple azimuth angles. For example, as the spacecraft passes over a particular location within the swath, the location is first observed looking, then a short while later the same location is observed looking backward. Over the orbit repeat cycle, the ground track shifts so that the same location is observed from a different set of azimuth angles for each pass. The precise distribution of azimuth angles depends on the orbit latitude, with the narrowest range near the equator and the largest range at high latitudes.

Note that there is a trade off between the imaging time period, the spatial resolution, and the azimuth sampling. Short time periods provide better temporal resolution for tracking sea ice motion and rapid freeze thaw events. However, short time periods provide inadequate coverage and/or azimuth sampling to reliably estimate the azimuth angle variation, particularly when the data is divided by local time of day. Recalling that the orbit repeat cycle is near-repeat after 4 days, we choose $N_d = 4$ days as the longest imaging intervals (N_d in days⁵). The imaging intervals are chosen to overlap by $N_d - 1$ days so they act like a N_d long moving average filter. Shorter N_d provides finer temporal resolution at the expense of reduced spatial coverage/resolution, including possible spatial artifacts in the reconstruction. These negative effects are reduced for the longer imaging intervals.

Note that a particular σ° observation (i.e., an ASCAT SZF 'slice') is an average of σ° in

⁴Sastrugi are wave-like features created by wind erosion and deposition of snow.

⁵Imaging intervals are specified in days, but may include only morning or evening (or descending or ascending) passes depending on the LTOD setting.

spatial coordinates as well as in azimuth and incidence angles. Within a single measurement the azimuth angle span and incidence angle spans within a single measurement are very small ($\ll 1^\circ$) and can be neglected. The roll off of σ° versus incidence angle, slightly biases the integrated measurement toward smaller incidence angles. This effect is neglected. Similarly, the variation of σ° within a particular slice footprint is neglected.

The variation in σ° as a function of azimuth and incidence angles for different measurements is important and provides useful geophysical information. Incidence angle variation is considered in the previous section. Of course, the variation in σ° as a function of azimuth enables wind retrieval over the ocean (Ulaby and Long, 2014)(Meissner et al., 2017). Azimuth variation (sometimes termed ‘azimuth modulation’) can be observed over snow dunes and sastrugi (Long and Drinkwater, 2000)(Ashcraft and Long, 2006)(Lindsley and Long, 2016) and sand dunes in ergs⁶ (Stephen and Long, 2007). As a result, significant azimuth variation in σ° is common over the Great Ice Sheets (GI) of Greenland and Antarctica, but is only rarely observed elsewhere over large regions with the exceptions of ergs.

For fan-beam scatterometers, since each satellite pass observes a given point on the surface from a limited azimuth angle, the variation of σ° with azimuth can lead to biases in the mean σ° value and to imaging artifacts when multiple passes with different azimuth angle observations are combined. To deal with azimuth variation of σ° on the GI, previous investigators, e.g., Long and Drinkwater (2000), Ashcraft and Long (2006), and Lindsley and Long (2016), have used a simple Fourier series model for the azimuth variation observed in σ° . Two models have been considered. One (here termed ‘FA’) with fixed azimuth modulation coefficients and the other (here termed ‘VA’) with incidence angle-dependent azimuth modulation coefficients. The azimuth modulation models can be expressed as

$$\sigma^\circ = A + B(\theta - 40) + M_1 \cos(\phi + P_1) + M_2 \cos(2\phi + P_2) \quad (11)$$

where ϕ is the azimuth angle, $M_1 = A_1$ and $M_2 = A_2$ for the FA model, and $M_1 = A_1 + R_1(\theta - 40)$ and $M_2 = A_2 + R_2(\theta - 40)$ for the VA model where A_1 and A_2 are the mean azimuth modulation coefficients and P_1 and P_2 are the phase angles relative to north. Note that the model can be with σ° in dB or linear space, though dB model have proven to be the most successful (Long and Drinkwater, 2000)(Lindsley and Long, 2016). Other azimuth modulation studies can be found in Ashcraft and Long (2006), Long and Drinkwater (2000), and Long and Miller (2022, 2023).

Following their work, we use a similar approach for modeling the azimuth variation of σ° for the azimuth image products described below. This technique, while applied globally, is most useful over the GI in the polar regions. Over other land areas, the amplitude of azimuth angle variation is small (though occasionally becomes visible as swath-related artifacts or in small image-to-image ‘oscillations’ in A due to variations in the distributions of the incidence and azimuth angles of observations).

⁶An erg landform is a large region or ‘sea’ of vegetation-free, wind-swept desert sand.

Figure 18: Incidence angle versus azimuth angle over DOYs 3-6, 2007 within in a particular Antarctic study region. The colors of the groupings correspond to different beams.

Unfortunately, with a maximum of only 3 azimuth angles in a single pass, the ASCAT polarization geometry is not very well suited for estimating the azimuth variation unless multiple passes are combined. Areas covered by both sides of the swath have the highest diversity of azimuth angle observations and thus the most accurate estimates of the azimuth variation. A complicating factor is that in the polar regions the incidence angle and azimuth angle of the observations at a given point can be coupled for the fan-beam geometry (Long and Drinkwater, 2000), see Figs. 18. Due to computational limitations, SIR products employ the azimuth dependence estimated using AVE images computed from all pass data to correct or adjust the σ^o values prior to using them in the SIR algorithm. This is recognized to be suboptimal, but is felt to be the best possible approach given the available sampling and computational limitations.

To illustrate the azimuth variation in the ASCAT data, Fig. 19 shows a scatter plots of the backscatter measurements over a study area in the dry snow zone in central Antarctica versus azimuth angle. Note the several dB azimuth modulation in this area. This results from sastrugi created by katabatic winds. The plot also illustrates the incomplete and variable density of the azimuth angle observations within this region. Other areas have different distributions with large gaps in the azimuth sampling. Note that the fit assumes spatial homogeneity; however, there is some spatial variability in the area has evident in Fig. 20 that provides maps of the estimated FA coefficients over the study region. For computational regions, these maps are created using 4 day AVE with all passes. The estimated azimuth model coefficients are used to ‘correct’ or adjust the measured σ^o values used in SIR processing.

Figures 21 and 22 illustrate AVE azimuth product images. Note that the estimation of

Figure 19: Scatter plots of ASCAT σ^o in dB versus azimuth angle for incidences angles between 35° and 45° for the study region in Antarctica shown in Fig. 18 for DOY 3-6, 2007. (left) Uncorrected σ^o measurements with a second-order FA model fit to the data shown as the red line. (right) Azimuth and incidence angle corrected σ^o measurements data using the FA model. Red line shows the mean (in dB) σ^o value.

the azimuth model coefficients assumes a stationary surface. Because of the wind variability over the ocean during the imaging period, the estimated azimuth model parameters should not be used over the ocean.

As described in Section 5.1, the PSRF is defined by the weighted combination of the MRFs of the measurements included in the pixel value. The weighting is determined by the choice of the algorithm used to create the image.

Unfortunately, the ASCAT measurement sampling does not fully cover the surface in a single pass, i.e., the surface is undersampled, so there are areas of pixels with only a single measurement available. For this case, the AVE (and therefore the SIR) image can only report this measurements' value over the area of its non-zero MRF and no resolution enhancement occurs. Further, it is impossible to compute the B value for the pixel.

In contrast, when multiple overlapping measurements are available, i.e., the surface is oversampled, it is possible to obtain images with finer effective resolution. Enhancement of the effective resolution *requires* dense sampling of the surface. This is the reason multiple passes are used. In addition, multiple measurements at a diversity of incidence angles are required to estimate the incidence angle slope and the azimuth modulation. When the surface is adequately sampled, the effective spatial resolution is improved, which can result in a reduction in noise. However, when the surface is undersampled, it is difficult for the image resolution to be much better than the MRF resolution.

Figure 20: Visualizations of the FA model coefficients for the Antarctic study region in Fig. 18 for DOY 3-6, 2007. The mean and standard deviation for the area in indicated in the panel title with the standard deviation in parenthesis.

Figure 21: Antarctica images extracted from Southern Hemisphere VV (left) σ^0 (A) and (right) azimuth corrected σ^0 (Az) product images for DOY 003-006, 2007.

6.3 Data Volume

Table 5 summarizes available CETB ASCAT radar products, which are all in CETB-standard EASE-2 Grid projections. In this table, “days” refers to the length of time used for image formation. Imaging periods overlap, with a new image started each day. Note that for LTOD images that in order to have the right number of morning or evening passes, the time period of the measurements actually used in the images may extend slightly outside the multi-day period. Individual file sizes vary due to internal file compression for each image type. See Section 4.5 for access details.

Figure 22: Antarctica images extracted from Southern Hemisphere VV σ^0 azimuth model coefficient images for DOY 003-006, 2007. (upper-left) A_1 magnitude. (upper-right) P_1 angle. (lower-left) A_2 magnitude. (lower-right) P_2 angle. The circular ring artifact surrounding the pole corresponds to where the swath coverage changes from single-side within the ring to dual-side outside of the ring. Note the circular color bar used for the P images.

7 Acknowledgements

This work utilizes resources from the Brigham Young University Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder and University of Colorado Boulder Research Computing Group, which is supported by the National Science Foundation (awards TBD), the University of Colorado Boulder and Colorado State University.

8 References

References

- Ashcraft, I. S. and D. G. Long. 2006. Relating microwave backscatter azimuth modulation to surface properties of the Greenland ice sheet. *Journal of Glaciology* 52(177), 257–266. doi:10.3189/172756506781828764.
- Attema, E.. 1991. The active microwave instrument on-board the ERS-1 satellite. *Proceeding of the IEEE* 79, 791—799. doi:10.1109/5.90158.
- Brodzik, M. J., B. Billingsley, T. Haran, B. Raup, and M. H. Savoie. 2012. EASE-Grid 2.0: Incremental but significant improvements for Earth-gridded data sets. *International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 1, 32–45. doi:10.3390/ijgi101003.
- Brodzik, M. J., B. Billingsley, T. Haran, B. Raup, and M. H. Savoie. 2014. Correction: Brodzik, M.J., *et al.* EASE-Grid 2.0: Incremental but Significant Improvements for Earth-Gridded Data Sets, *ISPRS Int. J. Geo-Inf.* 2012, 1, 32–45. *ISPRS Int. J. Geo-Inf.* 3, 1154–1156. doi:10.3390/ijgi3031154.
- Brodzik, M. J. and K. Knowles. 2011. EASE-Grid 2.0 Land-Ocean-Coastline-Ice Masks Derived from Boston University MODIS/Terra Land Cover Data. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center DAAC, Boulder, CO USA. Digital Media, <http://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-0610>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.5067/XR8523MC24TB>.
- Brodzik, M. J., D. G. Long, M. A. Hardman, A. Paget, and R. L. Armstrong. 2016, updated 2021. MEaSUREs Calibrated Enhanced-Resolution Passive Microwave Daily EASE-Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature ESDR, Version 1. National Snow and Ice Data Center, Boulder, CO USA. Digital Media, <http://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-0630>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.5067/MEASURES/CRYOSPHERE/NSIDC-0630.001>.
- Brodzik, M. J., J. M. Ramage, M. A. Hardman, D. G. Long, and R. L. Armstrong. 2018. Improving melt onset detection in mountainous regions from the new, enhanced-resolution passive microwave climate record. Poster presentation at EGU General Assembly, CR 2.1:10690, Vienna, Austria, 9–13 April.
- Early, D. S. and D. G. Long. 2001. Image reconstruction and enhanced resolution imaging from irregular samples. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 39(2), 291–302. doi:10.1109/36.905237.
- EUMETSAT. 2014. ASCAT level 1 SZV climate data record release 2 - metop. doi:<https://doi.org/https://navigator.eumetsat.int/product/EO:EUM:CM:METOP:ASCSZFR02>.

- EUMETSAT. 2022. ASCAT user guide. Doc. No. EUM/OPS-EPS/MAN/04/0028, doi:<https://doi.org/https://www-cdn.eumetsat.int/files/2022-12/ASCAT%20User%20Guide.pdf>.
- Gelsthorpe, R., E. Schied, and J. Wilson. 2000. ASCAT – metop’s advanced scatterometer. *ESA Bulletin 102*, 19–27. doi:<https://www.esa.int/esapub/bulletin/bullet102/Gelsthorpe102.pdf>.
- Lin, C.-C., W. Lengert, and E. Attema. 2017. Three generations of C-band wind scatterometer systems from ERS-1/2 to MetOp/ASCAT, and MetOp second generation. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing 10*(5), 2098–2122. doi:10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2616166.
- Lindsley, R., C. Anderson, J. F.-S. na, and D. Long. 2016. A parameterized ASCAT measurement spatial response function. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing 54*(8), 4570–4579. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2016.2544835.
- Lindsley, R. and D. Long. 2016. ASCAT and QuikSCAT azimuth modulation of backscatter over East Antarctica. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, 13*(8), 1134–1138. doi:10.1109/LGRS.2016.2572101.
- Long, D. and M. Brodzik. 2016a. Optimum image formation for spaceborne microwave radiometer products. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing 54*(5), 2763–2779. doi:10.1109/TGARS.2015.2505677.
- Long, D. and D. Daum. 1998. Spatial resolution enhancement of SSM/I data. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing 36*(2), 407–417. doi:10.1109/36.662726.
- Long, D. and M. Drinkwater. 2000. Azimuth variation in microwave scatterometer and radiometer data over Antarctica. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing 38*(4), 1857–1870. doi:10.1109/36.851769.
- Long, D. and R. Franz. 2016a. Band-limited signal reconstruction from irregular samples with variable apertures. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing 54*(4), 2424–2436. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2015.2501366.
- Long, D., P. Hardin, and P. Whiting. 1993. Resolution enhancement of spaceborne scatterometer data. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing 31*(3), 700–715. doi:10.1109/36.225536.
- Long, D. and J. Z. Miller. 2022. SMAP radar SAR and SIR-enhanced twice-daily EASE-grid 2.0 radar backscatter. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5067/SCKWZSWQ7HPL>.

- Long, D. and J. Z. Miller. 2023. NSCAT twice-daily SIR-enhanced scatterometer EASE-grid 2.0 radar backscatter. doi:<https://doi.org/TBD>.
- Long, D. G.. 2017. Comparison of SeaWinds backscatter imaging algorithms. *IEEE J. Sel. Topics in Applied Earth Observations* 10(3), 2214–2231. doi:10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2626966.
- Long, D. G. and M. J. Brodzik. 2016b, May. Optimum Image Formation for Spaceborne Microwave Radiometer Products. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 54(5), 2763–2779. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2015.2505677.
- Long, D. G., M. J. Brodzik, and M. A. Hardman. 2019. Enhanced-Resolution SMAP Brightness Temperature Image Products. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 57(7), 4151–4163. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2018.2889427.
- Long, D. G. and R. O. W. Franz. 2016b. Band-limited Signal Reconstruction from Irregular Samples with Variable Apertures. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 54(4), 2424–2436. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2015.2501366.
- Long, D. G. and J. Stroeve. 2011. Enhanced Resolution SSM/I and AMSR-E Daily Polar Brightness Temperatures, Version 1. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center, Boulder, CO USA. Digital Media, <http://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-0464>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.5067/MES22DNFS308>.
- Meissner, T., L. Ricciardulli, and F. J. Wentz. 2017. Capability of the SMAP mission to measure ocean surface winds in storms. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 98(8), 1660–1677. doi:10.1175/BAMS-D-16-0052.1.
- Naderi, F., M. H. Freilich, and D. G. Long. 1991. Spaceborne radar measurement of wind velocity over the ocean—an overview of the NSCAT scatterometer system. *Proceedings of the IEEE* 79(6), 850–866. doi:10.1109/5.90163.
- Pitas, I. and A. Venetsanopoulos. 1986. Nonlinear mean filters in image processing. *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing* 34(3), 573–584. doi:10.1109/TASSP.1986.1164857.
- Stephen, H. and D. G. Long. 2007. Spatial and temporal behavior of microwave backscatter directional modulation over the Saharan ergs. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 45(5), 1164–1173. doi:10.1109/TGRS.2007.892584.
- Stoffelen, A., S. Aaboe, J.-C. Calvet, J. Cotton, G. De Chiara, J. F. Saldaña, A. A. Mouche, M. Portabella, K. Scipal, and W. Wagner. 2017. Scientific developments and the EPS-SG scatterometer. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing* 10(5), 2086–2097. doi:10.1109/JSTARS.2017.2696424.

REFERENCES

REFERENCES

Ulaby, F. T. and D. G. Long. 2014. *Microwave Radar and Radiometric Remote Sensing*. Ann Arbor, MI, USA: University of Michigan Press.

Wikipedia. visited 8 Oct. 2016. Geometric mean. Online, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Geometric_mean.

Appendices

A ASCAT Projections and Grids

Table 6: ASCAT 25 km product EASE-Grid 2.0 projections and grid dimensions, produced for compatibility with CETB ESDR data products (Brodzik et al., 2021).

Name	Projection	Resolution (km)	Cols	Rows	Latitude Extent	Longitude Extent
EASE2-T25km	Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical	25.0	2600	1388	±67.057 640 6°	±180°
EASE2-T3.125km	Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical	3.125	15750	11104	±67.057 640 6°	±180°
EASE2-N25km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	25.0	720	720	0°–90°	±180°
EASE2-N3.125km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	3.125	5760	5760	0°–90°	±180°
EASE2-S25km	Southern Lambert Azimuthal	25.0	720	720	–90°–0°	±180°
EASE2-S3.125km	Southern Lambert Azimuthal	3.125	5760	5760	–90°–0°	±180°

B ASCAT Data Definition

B.1 File Requirements

Following Brodzik et al. (2021), *ASCAT* product file requirements include:

- Output file format shall be acceptable for NSIDC DAAC to easily ingest to ECS
- File size maximum will be < 1 GB (larger files are allowed in ECS, but fast network speeds cannot always be assumed)
- Files will conform to netCDF-CF 1.6 conventions for all but the requirement that puts the lat/lon arrays into the file; however, we will include CF-compliant coordinate variables with projected coordinate locations
- Files should pass CF-compliance-checking for all but the lat/lon arrays (we used JPL compliance-checker)
- Each file will contain 1 or more array variables, with associated ancillary variables, possibly different ancillary variables for each gridding technique. We may have a practical limit on the number of ancillary variables to include, limited by maximum file size
- Each file of the same type (GRD or SIR) will contain the same file-level metadata for that type.
- We will follow the DRY (Don't Repeat Yourself) principle: Metadata will not be duplicated at multiple places in the same file
- DRY exception: Time values will be machine- and human-readable
- DRY exception: Some projection metadata may be in multiple forms (a proj4 string and/or a WKT string)
- Variable/attribute names will be CF-compliant whenever possible

The *ASCAT* .nc files work with *gdal* utility, *gdal_translate*, to produce a geoTIFF version of each of the data variables <variable_name> in the file, (details in Brodzik et al. (2018)), for e.g.:

```
$ gdal_translate -of GTiff -b 1 \
NETCDF:''cetb.nc':<variable_name> variable_name.tif
```

B.2 Filename Convention

ASCAT data are distributed by the NSIDC DAAC (<http://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-TBD>).

Filenames are:

```
<product_id>-<grid_name>-<platform_sensor>-<yyyyddd>
-<channel_id>-<pass>-<algorithm>-<input_source>-<version>.nc
```

where parts of the filename are described in Table 7.

Table 7: ASCAT file naming convention

Part	Description	Values
<product_id>	NSIDC unique data product id	NSIDC-TBD
<grid_name>	EASE-Grid 2.0 grid id	See Table 6
<platform>	Satellite platform	ADEOS
<sensor>	Sensor name	ASCAT
<yyyyddd>	Date	4-digit year and 3-digit day-of-year
<channel_id>	Channel (frequency in GHz and polarization)	5.225VV
<pass>	Pass direction (T grids) or LTOD (N or S grids)	one of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B = Both (all measurements) • A = Ascending • D = Descending • M = Morning • E = Evening
<algorithm>	Reconstruction algorithm	one of GRD, AVE or SIR
<version>	Version number	production version number

B.3 File Content, v1.0

The following is a sample NetCDF *ncdump -h* utility output for a particular ASCAT v1.0 3.125 km SIR file. File-level metadata and processing details vary depending on projection, spatial resolution and processing details (method, input file list, etc.).

```
netcdf BYU-ASCAT-EASE2_N3.125km-METOP_ASCAT-2007003_2007006-5.3VV-B-SIR-v1.0 {
dimensions:
time = UNLIMITED ; // (1 currently)
y = 5760 ;
x = 5760 ;
variables:
double time(time) ;
time:standard_name = "time" ;
time:coverage_content_type = "coordinate" ;
time:long_name = "ANSI date" ;
time:units = "days since 1972-01-01 00:00:00" ;
time:calendar = "gregorian" ;
```

```
time:axis = "T" ;
time:valid_range = 0., 1.79769313486232e+308 ;
double y(y) ;
y:standard_name = "projection_y_coordinate" ;
y:coverage_content_type = "coordinate" ;
y:long_name = "y" ;
y:units = "meters" ;
y:axis = "Y" ;
y:valid_range = -9000000., 9000000. ;
double x(x) ;
x:standard_name = "projection_x_coordinate" ;
x:coverage_content_type = "coordinate" ;
x:long_name = "x" ;
x:units = "meters" ;
x:axis = "X" ;
x:valid_range = -9000000., 9000000. ;
char crs ;
crs:grid_mapping_name = "lambert_azimuthal_equal_area" ;
crs:longitude_of_projection_origin = 0. ;
crs:latitude_of_projection_origin = 90. ;
crs:false_easting = 0. ;
crs:false_northing = 0. ;
crs:semi_major_axis = 6378137. ;
crs:inverse_flattening = 298.257223563 ;
crs:proj4text = "+proj=laea +lat_0=90 +lon_0=0 +x_0=0 +y_0=0 +ellps=WGS84 +datum=WGS84 +";
crs:srid = "urn:ogc:def:crs:EPSG::6931" ;
crs:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
crs:references = "[\"EASE-Grid 2.0 documentation: http://nsidc.org/data/ease/ease\_grid2\"";
crs:crs_wkt = "PROJCRS[\"WGS 84 / NSIDC EASE-Grid 2.0 North\", BASEGEODCRS[\"WGS 84\", D";
crs:long_name = "EASE2_N3.125km" ;
short Sigma0_ave(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_ave:long_name = "AVE Sigma0" ;
Sigma0_ave:units = "1" ;
Sigma0_ave:comment_on_units = "unitless, stored as dB=10*log10()" ;
Sigma0_ave:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_ave:valid_range = 0s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_ave:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_ave:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_offset";
Sigma0_ave:scale_factor = 0.002f ;
Sigma0_ave:add_offset = -55.f ;
```

```
Sigma0_ave:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_ave:coverage_content_type = "image" ;
short Sigma0_slope_ave(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:long_name = "AVE Sigma0 slope" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:units = "1" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:comment_on_units = "dB/deg, dB=10*log10()" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:valid_range = 0s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_
Sigma0_slope_ave:scale_factor = 0.001f ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:add_offset = -2.f ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:coverage_content_type = "image" ;
short Sigma0(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0:long_name = "SIR Sigma0" ;
Sigma0:units = "1" ;
Sigma0:comment_on_units = "unitless, stored as dB=10*log10()" ;
Sigma0:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0:valid_range = 0s, 32767s ;
Sigma0:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_offset" ;
Sigma0:scale_factor = 0.002f ;
Sigma0:add_offset = -55.f ;
Sigma0:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0:coverage_content_type = "image" ;
Sigma0:sir_number_of_iterations = 30 ;
Sigma0:median_filter = 1 ;
Sigma0:temporal_division = "Both" ;
Sigma0:temporal_division_local_start_time = 5.f ;
Sigma0:temporal_division_local_end_time = 17.f ;
Sigma0:frequency_and_polarization = "5.3VV" ;
short Sigma0_slope(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_slope:long_name = "SIR Sigma0 slope" ;
Sigma0_slope:units = "1" ;
Sigma0_slope:comment_on_units = "dB/deg, dB=10*log10()" ;
Sigma0_slope:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_slope:valid_range = 0s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_slope:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_slope:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_offs
```

```
Sigma0_slope:scale_factor = 0.001f ;
Sigma0_slope:add_offset = -2.f ;
Sigma0_slope:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_slope:coverage_content_type = "image" ;
short Sigma0_num_samples(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_num_samples:long_name = "SIR Number of Measurements" ;
Sigma0_num_samples:units = "count" ;
Sigma0_num_samples:_FillValue = 0s ;
Sigma0_num_samples:valid_range = 1s, 255s ;
Sigma0_num_samples:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_num_samples:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
short Incidence_angle(time, y, x) ;
Incidence_angle:standard_name = "angle_of_incidence" ;
Incidence_angle:long_name = "SIR Incidence Angle" ;
Incidence_angle:units = "degree" ;
Incidence_angle:_FillValue = -1s ;
Incidence_angle:valid_range = 0s, 9000s ;
Incidence_angle:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Incidence_angle:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_o
Incidence_angle:scale_factor = 0.01f ;
Incidence_angle:add_offset = 0.f ;
Incidence_angle:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Incidence_angle:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
short Sigma0_std_dev(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_std_dev:long_name = "SIR Sigma0 standard deviation" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:units = "1" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:comment_on_units = "unitless, stored as dB=10*log10()" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_std_dev:valid_range = -32766s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_std_dev:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_of
Sigma0_std_dev:scale_factor = 0.002f ;
Sigma0_std_dev:add_offset = 0.f ;
Sigma0_std_dev:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
short Sigma0_time(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_time:long_name = "Time of Day" ;
Sigma0_time:units = "minutes since 2007-01-03 00:00:00" ;
Sigma0_time:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_time:valid_range = -32767s, 32767s ;
```

```
Sigma0_time:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_time:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_offset" ;
Sigma0_time:scale_factor = 1.f ;
Sigma0_time:add_offset = 0.f ;
Sigma0_time:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_time:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
Sigma0_time:calendar = "gregorian" ;

// global attributes:
:references = "Early, D. S., and D.G. Long. 2001. Image Reconstruction and Enhanced Resolution  
:title = "ASCAT Radar Twice-Daily SIRF-Enhanced EASE-Grid 2.0 Sigma0" ;
:id = "doi:TBD" ;
:summary = "Enhanced-resolution, gridded ASCAT Ku-band radar backscatter" ;
:project = "Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder" ;
:contributor_name = "David G. Long, NASA Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder" ;
:contributor_role = "Principal Investigator and Developer, Data Producer" ;
:citation = "D. G. Long\nASCAT Twice-Daily SIRF-Enhanced EASE-Grid 2.0 Sigma0.\nVersion 1.0.0" ;
:license = "These data are freely, openly, and fully available to use without restriction" ;
:Conventions = "CF-1.6, ACDD-1.3" ;
:product_version = "v1.0" ;
:software_version_id = "1.0.0" ;
:software_repository = "" ;
:history = "ascat_meta_sir_cetb" ;
:comment = "Epoch date for data in this file: 2007-01-03 00:00:00Z" ;
:source = ": See input_fileN list and number_of_input_files attributes" ;
:metadata_link = "http://www.scp.byu.edu/" ;
:institution = "Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder\nElectrical and Computer Engineering Department" ;
:publisher_name = "Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder" ;
:publisher_type = "institution" ;
:publisher_url = "http://www.scp.byu.edu" ;
:publisher_email = "long@ee.byu.edu" ;
:program = "NASA Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS)" ;
:standard_name_vocabulary = "CF Standard Name Table (v27, 28 September 2013)" ;
:cdm_data_type = "Grid" ;
:keywords = "EARTH SCIENCE > SPECTRAL/ENGINEERING > MICROWAVE > RADAR BACKSCATTER" ;
:keywords_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Earth Science Keyword List" ;
:platform = "OSCAT > ISRO scatterometer on OceanSat-2" ;
:platform_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Earth Science Keyword List" ;
:instrument = "ASCAT C-BAND RADAR > ASCAT C-Band Radar" ;
:instrument_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Earth Science Keyword List"
```

```
:time_coverage_resolution = "P1d" ;
:geospatial_lat_min = 0. ;
:geospatial_lat_max = 90. ;
:geospatial_lon_min = -180. ;
:geospatial_lon_max = 180. ;
:naming_authority = "org.doi.dx" ;
:date_created = "2024-04-21T01:48:28GMT" ;
:date_modified = "2024-04-21T01:48:28GMT" ;
:date_issued = "2024-04-21T01:48:28GMT" ;
:date_metadata_modified = "2024-04-21T01:48:28GMT" ;
:input_data_quality_filtering = "Only used highest-quality input data." ;
:acknowledgement = "This data set was created with funding from NASA Grant #TBD." ;
:processing_level = "Level 3" ;
:creator_name = "David Long" ;
:creator_type = "person" ;
:creator_email = "long@ee.byu.edu" ;
:creator_url = "http://www.scp.byu.edu" ;
:creator_institution = "Electrical and Computer Engineering Department\nBrigham Young Un
:geospatial_lat_units = "degrees_north" ;
:geospatial_lon_units = "degrees_east" ;
:geospatial_x_resolution = "3125.00 meters" ;
:geospatial_y_resolution = "3125.00 meters" ;
:time_coverage_start = "2007-01-02T23:59:00.00Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "2007-01-03T23:41:00.00Z" ;
:time_coverage_duration = "P00T23:42:00.00" ;
:number_of_input_files = 56 ;
:input_file1 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103002100Z_20070103020559Z_R_0_20140127105040Z" ;
:input_file2 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103020600Z_20070103034759Z_R_0_20140127105101Z" ;
:input_file3 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103034800Z_20070103052959Z_R_0_20140127105102Z" ;
:input_file4 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103053000Z_20070103071159Z_R_0_20140127105103Z" ;
:input_file5 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103071200Z_20070103085359Z_R_0_20140127105122Z" ;
:input_file6 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103085400Z_20070103103559Z_R_0_20140127105128Z" ;
:input_file7 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103103600Z_20070103121459Z_R_0_20140127105130Z" ;
:input_file8 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103121500Z_20070103135359Z_R_0_20140127105129Z" ;
:input_file9 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103135400Z_20070103153559Z_R_0_20140127105132Z" ;
:input_file10 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103153600Z_20070103171459Z_R_0_20140127105535Z" ;
:input_file11 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103171500Z_20070103185659Z_R_0_20140127105555Z" ;
:input_file12 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103185700Z_20070103203559Z_R_0_20140127105628Z" ;
:input_file13 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103203600Z_20070103221759Z_R_0_20140127105628Z" ;
:input_file14 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070103221800Z_20070103235959Z_R_0_20140127105628Z" ;
```

```
:input_file15 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070104014200Z_20070104032659Z_R_0_20140127105728Z" ;

```

```
:input_file55 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070106211500Z_20070106225659Z_R_0_20140127111610Z" ;  
:input_file56 = "ASCA_SZF_1B_M02_20070106225700Z_20070107003859Z_R_0_20140127111653Z" ;  
}
```